

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

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To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

CONTENTS

Preface	7
Introductory	8
Methods of experimental scurvy, from Holst to the latest investigators	9

Part I.

Examination of the antiscorbutic value of some vegetable products.

Survey of experiments	18
Summary; discussion; conclusions	22

Part II.

Histo-pathological studies.

Preliminary notes.

Introductory	29
The macroscopic changes	30
Technique	31
Nomenclature	32
Classification of scurvy in different stages	33
Grouping of the material within these stages	36
Chapter I. The bone formation in scurvy.	
Teeth	38
The endosomal ossification	48
The enchondral ossification. Cartilage	50
*	
Four cases of infantile scurvy	60
*	
Summary and conclusions of Chapter I.	64
Chapter II. Muscles.	
The skeleton musculature	68
Heart	79
Chapter III. Liver	82
Chapter IV. Spleen	91
Chapter V. Kidney	96
Chapter VI. Adrenal	100
Chapter VII. Salivary glands	104
Chapter VIII. Lung	107
Chapter IX. Blood and vessels. Hemorrhages in scurvy	109
Chapter X. Connective tissue	114

Part III.

Discussion of some scurvy problems.

Chapter I. Scurvy and infection	115
Chapter II. Disposition	122
Chapter III. Latent scurvy	123
Chapter IV. The calcium metabolism in scurvy	126
Chapter V. Scurvy and rickets	128
Chapter VI. Inanition and scurvy	129
Chapter VII. A modified method for experimental rating of the antiscorbutic value of a product	130
Chapter VIII. Pathogenesis of scurvy. Relation of scurvy to other deficiency diseases	132

<i>Summary and conclusions of Parts II and III</i>	139
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Part IV.

Scurvy and tuberculosis.

Chapter I. Historical	140
Chapter II. Experimental study on guinea-pig. Technique and survey of experiments	148
Influence of scurvy on tuberculosis	154
Influence of tuberculosis on scurvy	162
Chapter III. Experimental study on man. Survey of experiment	164
Criticism and conclusion	169

<i>Summary and conclusions of Part IV</i>	170
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Part V.

Records of cases.

Cases belonging to Part I	172
" " " " II, Chapter I	200
" " " " IV, " II	206
" " " " IV, " III	234
Literature cited:	265
List of authors	275

94 microphotograms.
33 curves in the text.
6 colored plates.

Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDÉLL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMÉLL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

Fig. 1. Location of the section at right angles to the longitudinal axis of the lower jaw through the middle of the first molar.

Fig. 2. Diagrammatic section through the lower jaw.
j jaw-bone, *mu* muscles of tongue, *sl. gl.* glandula sublingualis, *i* cross section of root of incisor., *mo* longitudinal section of molar, *can. m.* canalis mandibulae with vessels and nerves.

Fig. 3. No scurvy. No. 188.

Cross section of normal incisor. Low power.

j jaw-bone, *pe od* periodontium, *c m* cement membrane, *d* dentin, *pred* predentin, *od bl* odontoblasts, *pu* pulp, *am bl* amyloblasts, *v* bloodvessels, *e* enamel.

Fig. 4. Scorbut latens gravior, 8 days. No. 38.

Cross section of incisor. The predentin (*pred*) is amorphously calcified.

d dentin, *e* enamel, *sl gl* sublingual gland, *c m* the widened canalis mandibule.

Fig. 5. Scorbut latens gravior, 12 days. No. 29. Predentin (*pred*) amor- phously calcified, Tomes' canals (*d.c.*) widened. Odontoblasts (*od bl*) in disorder. *e* enamel.

Fig. 6. Scorbut latens mitior. No. 18. Cross section of incisor. Bone (*pb*) growing into pulp *ost bl* osteoblasts, *v* dilated vein, *od bl* odontoblasts in disorder, *pe od* periodontium, *j* jaw-bone.

Fig. 7 a. Detail of Fig. 6, from the oral side of the incisor

od bl odontoblasts in disorder, *b* hard tissue, looking like amorphous cement, *d* old dentin, *pu* pulp.

Fig. 7 b. Detail of Fig. 6 from the opposite side to Fig. 7 a.

ost bl osteoblasts, *pb* pulva bone, *dc* old Tomes' canals, widened, *pu* pulp, *b* amorphous bone.

Fig. 8. Scorbut mitior manifestus. 0.1 m. pr. d., 60 days. No. 58.

Cross section of incisor. Low power. Osteoblasts (*ost bl*) fill the pulp. Between them a homogeneous substance, osteoid (*ost*).

pb pulpa bone, *d* dentin, *c m* cement membrane, *pe od* periodontium, *j* jaw-bone, *v* dilated vessel.

Fig. 9. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 28 days. No. 25.

Cross section of incisor. Low power. Bone (*pb*) growing into pulp. Osteoblasts (*ost bl*) fill the pulp. Between them osteoid (*ost*).

sp hydropic spaces, *v* dilated vein, *h* hemorrhage, *d* dentin, *c m* cement membrane, *pe od* periodontium, *j* jaw-bone.

Fig. 10. Scorbut manifestus mitior 0.1 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Cross section of lower jaw. Formation of bone
of spongy character in the pulp (*pb*) and on the
outside of the jaw (*sp j b*).

c m canalis mandibulae, dilated, *sp* hydropic space, *sl gl* sub-
lingual gland, *j* old jaw-bone.

Fig. 11. Detail of Fig. 10 (high power),
showing the canals in the porotic pulp bone.

ost bl osteoblasts.

ost.
bl.

Fig. 12. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 23 days.
No. 57.

Longitudinal section of molar, high power, showing
the canals in the spongy, porous bone.

ost bl osteoblasts.

can.m.

od.
bl.

ost.bl

Fig. 13. Same as Fig. 12, low power.
The pulpa bone gets stronger the more it
approaches the crown.

od bl odontoblasts, *ost bl* osteoblasts, *can m* canalis mandibularis, dilated, *i* incisior.

Fig. 14. Scurbut manifestus gravior, 24 days.
No. 1.

Cross section of incisor. Low power. Slight layer
of pulpa bone (*pb*).

pu pulp, *d* dentin, *er* remains of enamel, *v* dilated vein.

Fig. 15. Scurbut manifestus gravior, 30 days.
No. 50.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Resorption
of pulpa bone.

pb remains of pulpa bone, *sp* hydropic spaces, *d* dentin,
cm cement membrane, *pe.od* periodontium.

Fig. 16. Detail of Fig. 15, high power.
pb remains of pulpa bone bridges, *d* dentin, *pu* pulp.

Fig. 17. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 30 days.

No. 23.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Resorption
of pulpa bone (*pb*).

h hemorrhage, *nec* necrosis, *pe od* periodontium, *d* dentin.

Fig. 18. Scorbut manifestus mitior, 46 days.
No. 75.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Pulp bone
(*pb*) fills the pulp.

ost bl osteoblasts, *pe od* periodontium.

Fig. 19. Healing scurvy. No. 76.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Osteodentin
(*ost d*) fills the pulp.

Hav can bone canals.

Fig. 20. Detail of Fig. 19.
dent can dental canal, *od bl* odontoblasts.

Fig. 21. Healing scurvy: No. 78.
 Cross section of incisor, low power. In the dentin,
 which is folded and irregular, bone canals (*Hav can*)
 are seen in the outer layer.
od bl irregular odontoblasts, *pe od* periodontium, *j* jaw bone,
ost d osteodentin, *d* dentin.

Fig. 22. Scorbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m.
pr. d. 42 days. No. 122.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Pulp bone
(*pb*) fills the pulp.

d old dentin with dilated *d c* Tomes' canals.

Fig. 23. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0.2 m. pr. d. 29 days. No. 130.

Cross section of incisor, low power. Pulp bone (*pb*)
fills the pulp.

d old dentin with dilated *dent can* Tomes' canals.

Fig. 24. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0.3 m. pr. d. 83 days. No. 135.

Cross section of incisor, low power.

pb pulpa bone, *obl* odontoblasts in disorder, *ost.bl* osteoblasts.

Fig. 25. Scorbut mitior latens levior,
0.5 m. pr. d. 92 days. No. 144.

ost.d osteodentin, *pb* pulpa bone, *Hav can.* bone canals,
d dentin *d.c.* dental canals.

Fig. 26. *Scorbut mitior latens levior*,
0,7 m. pr. d. 22 days. No. 152.

Abbreviations = Fig. 25.

Fig. 27. *Scorbut mitior latens levior*,
0,7 m. pr. d. 92 days. No. 156.

Abbreviations = Fig. 25.

Fig. 28. Scorbut mitior latens levior,
0.8 m. pr. d. 29 days. No. 159.
Old dentin (*d*) without distinct changes. New
dentin (*n d*) lighter, with irregular inner edge.
od bl odontoblasts in disorder.

Fig. 29. Scorbut mitior latens levior,
0.8 m. pr. d. 92 days. No. 161.
Abbreviations = Fig. 28.

Fig. 30. No scurvy. > 1 m. pr. d. No. 176.
pe od periodontium, *d* dentin, *pred* predentin, *ost bl* osteoblasts, *pu* pulp, *j* jaw bone.

Fig. 31. Scurbit manifestus gravior, 38 days.
 No. 3.

Oblique cross section of molar. No free pulp. but in the medullary spaces (*med sp*) and bone canals (*Hav can*) pulp cells are seen.

Fig. 32. No scurvy.

Section of embryonic jaw.

m molar, *j* jaw-bone, *d* dentin, *od bl* odontoblasts.

Fig. 33. Scurbut manifestus mitior, 0.2 m. pr. d.
42 days. No. 67.

Cross section of lower jaw, high power. Formation of spongy bone (*sp b*) outside the old jaw (*j*), which shows osteoporosis. *med sp* medullary spaces, dilated, *m* apex of molar with pulpa bone (*pb*).

Fig. 34. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 24 days.
No. 1.

Cross section of lower jaw, high power. Resorption of the new, spongy bone.

ost. cl. "osteoclasts".

Fig. 35. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0.3 m. pr. d. 43 days. No. 140.

Frontal section of rib. Periosteal bone of spongy character.

mu. atrophied muscle, *c. c.* cartilage columns, low.

Fig. 36. No scurvy. No. 96.

Frontal section of rib. Normal picture.

cc cartilage columns, *b* bone, *ma* marrow, *c* cartilage, *pe* periosteum, *mu* muscles.

Fig. 37. Scurbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m. pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Frontal section of rib, showing typical scorbutic changes in the enlarged costochondral junction.

c cartilage, *cc* cartilage columns in disorder, *calc c* primarily calcified cartilage, growing into the marrow, *hom b* homogeneous scorbutic bone, in the outer angle connected with cartilage and bone columns, *pe b* spongy periosteal bone, *fr w m* frame-work marrow, *v* dilated vein, *p* periosteum, *mu* atrophied muscle fibres, *b* old bone bridge, *h* hemorrhage.

Fig. 38. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0.3 m. pr. d. 77 days. No. 139.

Frontal section of rib, one angle; high power.
Inferior bone (*hom b*), joins cartilage (*c*) and
old bone (*b*).

Fig. 39. Scorbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Frontal section of rib, high power. In the homo-
geneous new bone (*hom b*) there are canaliculi (*can*).
c cartilage, *b* old bone bridges and calcified cartilage.

Fig. 40. Scurbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Frontal section of rib, detail, high power.

ma bone marrow, deficient in cells, *b* bone bridges, *hom b* homogeneous new scorbutic bone, *can* canaliculi, *ost bl* osteoblasts, spool-shaped.

Fig. 41. Scurbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m.
pr. d. 50 days. No. 69.

Frontal section of rib, low power. Stained according to v. Kossa.

Calc b calcified cartilage and bone, *fr w m* frame-work marrow.

a

b

Fig. 42. Radiogram of the front chest wall of scorbutic
(*a*) and normal (*b*) guinea-pig. a No 68, b No 189.

The dark shadow in the anterior epiphyses of the ribs in scurvy
is clearly demonstrated.

Fig. 43. Scorbut manifestus mitior, 0.1 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Abundant formation of new scorbutic bone (*hom b.*).

b old bone, *c* cartilage, *calc* c primarily calcified cartilage,
bas se b basophile scorbutic bone, *pe b* periosteal bone,
fr fracture, *fr w m* frame-work marrow, *h* hemorrhage.

Fig. 44. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 24 days. No. 1.

Frontal section of rib, low power.

c cartilage, *cc* cartilage columns, *low*, *b* bone, *fr* fracture, *fr w m* frame-work marrow, *h* hemorrhage.

Fig. 45. Scorbut manifestus mitior, 46 days. No. 75.

a) Frontal section of rib, low power. b) Detail, high power. In the swollen costochondral junction there is an abundant formation of inferior bone in both angles.

hom b homogeneous scorbutic new bone, *can* canaliculi, numerous, *b* old bone, *prim calc c* primarily calcified cartilage, *c* cartilage, *fr w m* frame-work marrow, *pe b* periosteal spongy bone, *ma* hyperemic marrow, *h* hemorrhage.

Fig. 46. Scurvy healing since 30 days.

Frontal section of rib. a) Low power, No. 76. b) High power No. 77. Remains of the homogeneous scorbutic bone (*hom b*) is seen in several places in the system of normal bone columns (*n b*).

c cartilage.

Fig. 47. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 24 days.

No. 1.

Longitudinal section of the tibia, lower end; high power. Homogeneous new scorbutic bone (*hom b*) in resorption.

ost cl »osteoclasts», syncytium of bone-cells.

Fig. 48. Frontal section of rib, embryonal.

prim calc c primarily calcified cartilage.

Fig. 49 a. Infantile scurvy, Case 1.
Irregular pieces of bone (*i b*) are present in the system of more normal bone columns (*n b*). Femur, lower epiphyseal end. High power.

Fig. 49 b. Infantile scurvy, Case 1.
In the angle between periosteum (*p*) and cartilage (*c*) there are numerous splinters of poorly developed bone (*sc b*). Tibia, upper end. Low power.

Fig. 49 c. Infantile scurvy, Case 1.
Homogeneous place (*hom b*) in otherwise more normal bone. Tibia, upper end. High power.

Fig. 50. Infantile scurvy. Case 3.
Femur, upper epiphysis. High power. Old bone columns (*n b*) through abundant homogeneous scorbutic bone (*hom b*) joined to cartilage (*c*).

Fig. 51. Infantile scurvy. Case 4.

Rib, posterior end. Bone columns (*n b*), lying in the frame-work marrow (*fr w m*), joined to the cartilage (*c*) through a system of more homogeneous bone (*hom b*).

Fig. 52. No scurvy, 142 days.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power. Normal muscle.

Mu muscle fibre, *pe* periosteum, *b* bone, *ap* adipose tissue.

Fig. 53. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 32 days. No. 28.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power. Atrophy of the muscle fibres (*mu*). Dilatation of the veins (*v*).

Fig. 54. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 26 days. No. 21.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power. The same muscular atrophy is seen all through as in the neighbourhood of the hemorrhages (*he*). *v* dilated vessels, *scorb b* new homogeneous scorbutic bone in the costal angle, *pe* periosteum.

Fig. 55. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,1 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power.
Atrophy of muscle fibres, partly homogenized (*hom*),
partly with remaining cross-striation (*cr str*).

Fig. 56. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0.1 m. pr. d.
60 days. No. 58.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power. Atrophy
of the muscle fibres (*mu*). Connective tissue (*c t*) increased.

Fig. 57. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 38 days.
No. 3.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. High power. Atrophy of muscle fibres. Cross-striation (*cr str*) remaining in the fine fibres.

h d homogenized dot.

Fig. 58. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,2
m. pr. d. 60 days. No. 58.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Low power. Atrophic muscle (*mu*) with large calcified necrosis (*necr*).

pe periosteum, *b* bone, *v* dilated vessels in the hyperemic marrow.

Fig. 59. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 22 days,
No. 48.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. High power.
Calcified necrosis (*necr*) of muscle fibres.

Fig. 60. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0,3 m. pr. d. 29 days. No. 63.

Longitudinal section of elbow. High power. Atrophic
muscle with increased connective tissue (*ct*)
and calcified necrosis (*necr*).

Fig 61. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,2 m.
pr. d. 59 days. No. 88.

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Very high power. Giant-nuclei cells (*gn*) in atrophic muscle.

Fig. 62. Scorbut manifestus gravior, 35 days.
No. 35

Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Very high power. Giant-nuclei cells (*gn*) in atrophic muscle.

Fig. 63. Healing scurvy. No. 77.
 Longitudinal section of rib interstice. Very high power. Regeneration of muscle.
c t connective tissue, *cap* capillaries, *reg mu c* giant syncytial muscle cell of regenerative type.

Fig. 64. Healing scurvy. No. 77.
 Longitudinal section of knee. Very high power. Rest of necrotic fibres (*necr*) remaining. Connective tissue (*c t*) increased.

Fig. 65, a and b. Infantile scurvy. Case 3.
Longitudinal section of thigh. High power. Atrophy of muscle fibres (*mu*).
The interstitial tissue (*i t*) looks edematous.

Fig. 66. Scurbut mitior latens levior, 0,8 m. pr. d. 92 days. No. 161.
Longitudinal section of heart. The musculature looks normal.

Fig. 67. Scurbut gravior manifestus, 19 days. No. 113.
Longitudinal section, heart. Muscle fibres homogenized, thickened, stained deeply by eosin.
v dilated vessels.

Fig. 68. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,5 m.
pr. d. 18 days. No. 145.

Longitudinal section of heart. Low power. Calcium pigment (*ca*) in the fine, atrophic muscle fibres (*mu*).

Fig. 69 Detail of Fig. 68. Very high
power.

Calcium pigment deposited so as to make the cross-striation structure manifest.

Fig. 70. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,2 m.
pr. d. 43 days. No. 132.

Longitudinal section of heart. Very high power.
The calcium pigment in the atrophic muscle fibres
deposited so as to make the cross-striation structure
manifest.

Fig. 71 No scurvy. No. 1.
Liver. Normal picture. Low power.

Fig. 72. Scorbutus gravior manifestus, 37 days. No. 41.

Liver. Low power. Atrophy.

v central vein.

Fig. 73. Scorbutus gravior manifestus, 35 days. No. 35.

Liver. Low power. Atrophy.

li.co thin liver columns.

Fig. 74. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 30 days. No. 45.
Liver. Low power. Large necroses (*necr*).

Fig. 75 Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,2 m. pr. d. 39 days. No. 84.

Liver, sudan. Low power. Large necroses (*necr*) with small fat drops diffusely, larger (*lip*) at the edge.

Fig. 76. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,2 m. pr. d., 43 days. No. 86.

Liver. Low power. Calcified necrosis (*neer*) with fibroblasts in the periphery.

Fig. 77. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 28 days. No. 73.

Liver. Low power. Large irregular necroses, some with bilious pigment (*liv pigm*), others calcified (*ca*)

Fig. 78. Scorbut mitior manifestus. 0,2 m. pr. d.
43 days. No. 86.
Liver stained according to v. Kossa. Low power. Large
necroses, surrounded by calcified grains.

Fig. 79. No Scurvy. No. 11.
Spleen. Low power. Normal picture.
g c Malpighian corpuscle.

Fig. 80. Scorbut gravior manifestus, 37 days.
No. 41.

Spleen. Low power. Atrophy of the lymphoid tissue, especially in the Malpighian corpuscles (*g c*).

Fig. 81. Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,3 m. pr. d.
60 days. No. 58.

Spleen. Low power. Atrophy of the lymphoid tissue, especially in the periphery of the Malpighian corpuscles (*g c*).

Fig. 82. No scurvy. No. 11.
Spleen. High power. Normal picture of pulp.
Lymphocytes (*lf*) numerous.

Fig. 83. Scurbut gravior manifestus, 37
days. No. 41.
Spleen. High power. Atrophy of the lymphoid
tissue. The lymphocytes (*lf*) very sparse.

Fig. 84. Scurbut mitior manifestus, 0,1 m. pr. d.
15 days. No. 120.
Spleen, infection. Low power. Lymphocytic reaction weak.
Numerous necroses (*necr.*).
g c Malpighian corpuscles.

g.c.

necr.

g.c.

necr.

he.

necr.

necr.

Fig. 85. Scurbut mitior latens extensus, 0,3 m.
pr. d. 40 days. No. 138.
Spleen, infection. Low power. Weak lymphocytic reaction.
Large necroses (*necr.*) and hemorrhages (*he.*).

Fig. 86. No scurvy. No. 168.
Kidney, cortex. Low power. Normal picture.
gl glomeruli, *tub* tubules.

Fig. 87. Scurbut gravior manifestus, 19 days.
No. 113.
Kidney, cortex. Low power. Atrophy with shrunk
glomeruli (*gl*).
v dilated vessels.

Fig. 88 a. Scorbut mitior latens extensus, 0.3 m.
pr. d. 76 days. No. 142.

Kidney, marrow. High power. Calcium concretion (*calc.*).
calc calcium between the nucleus and capillary (*cap*) of the epithe-
lium cells.

Fig. 88 b. Scorbut mitior latens extensus,
0.3 m. pr. d. 76 days. No. 142.

tub calcified tubules, *ep* epithelium cells.

tub.

Fig. 88 c. Scorbut mitior latens extensus, 0.3 m.
pr. d. 76 days. No. 142.
tub calcified tubule.

calc.

Fig. 88 d. Scorbut mitior latens extensus, 0.3 m.
pr. d. 76 days. No. 142.
calc calcium concretion in the lumen of a tubule.

a

b

Fig. 89. Scorbut mitior latens levior, 0.8 m. pr. d., 82 days. No. 161.
Kidney, marrow. High power.

a) *calc* calcium concretion, subepithelially, bulging the epithelium (*ep*) in the lumen of a tubule (*tub*). b) *calc* calcium concretion in the free lumen of a tubule (*tub*).

Fig. 90. Scorbut mitior latens extensus, 0.3 m. pr. d.,
83 days. No. 135.
Kidney, marrow. High power.
calc calcium concretion in the wall of a tubule (*tub*).

Fig. 91 a. Convalescence of beriberi. No. 83.
Kidney, marrow. High power.
calc calcium concretion subepithelially, *tub* tubule.

b

c

Fig. 91 b, c.

calc calcium concretion in the lumen of a tubule (*tub*).

Fig. 92. No scurvy. No. 178.

Adrenal. Low power. Normal picture.

z glom zona glomerulosa, *z fasc* zona fasciculata, *z ret* zona reticularis *med* medulla.

Fig. 93. Scurbut mitior manifestus, 0.1 m. pr. d., 25 days. No. 121.

Adrenal. Low power. Atrophy, hyperemia.

z glom zona glomerulosa, *z fasc* zona fasciculata, *z ret* zona reticularis, *v* dilated vessel.

Fig. 94. No scurvy. Relative inanition.
No. 186.

Adrenal. Low power. Atrophy light, hyperemia strong.

z glom zona glomerulosa, *z fasc* zona fasciculata, *z ret* zona reticularis, *med* medulla, *he* hemorrhage, *cap* dilated capillaries.

Scorbut manifestus mitior. No. 75.

Frontal section of rib, $\times 28$.

Connective tissue staining of Hansen.

Atrophy of the collagen substance in cartilage (*c*) and bone (*b*).

No collagen in the new scorbutic bone (*hom. b.*).

m. k. megakaryocytes. *fr. w. m.* frame-work marrow.

Healing scurvy. No. 76.

Frontal section of rib, $\times 28$.

Connective tissue staining of Hansen.

Reorganisation of the costochondral junction.

Remaining beams of collagen-free bone (*hom. b.*) enclosed in the system of more normal bone-columns (*b.*).

No scurvy. Complete dietary. No. 108. 102 days.
Tuberculous focus in muscle. Necroses penetrated and surrounded
by connective tissue with strong collagen fibrils.

Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,1 m. pr. d. 24 days. No. 124.
Tuberculous focus in musculo. Necrosis. Inconsiderable collagen
substance.

No scurvy. Complete dietary. No. 172. 24 days.
Tuberculous necroses in regional lymph gland, penetrated and
surrounded by connective tissue with strong collagen fibrils.

Scorbut mitior manifestus, 0,1 m. pr. b. 43 days.
Tuberculous necroses in regional lymphglands. Inconsiderable
collagen substance.